

Online Oral Presentation #22 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Sevgi Cirakli
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7992-1376>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University, Education and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Another cause of gait disorders is peroneal nerve damage. The peroneal nerve, which branches off from the sciatic nerve in the popliteal fossa, passes the lateral head of the gastrocnemius muscle on the outer surface of the popliteal fossa. The peroneal nerve provides plantar flexion of the foot. Since plantar flexion cannot be performed in its damage, drop foot clinic occurs. Patients present with complaints of impaired walking.

Materials and Methods: 4 cases that applied with drop foot clinic between January 2018 and January 2025 were examined.

Results: 3 of the patients (75%) were male, 1 was female (25%). The clinic of 3 of the patients (75%) was due to trauma and 1 (25%) was secondary to viral infections. All of those due to trauma were male, and peroneal nerve damage was observed on one side of the leg in the trauma area. In the only case that developed viral infection, the findings were observed bilaterally. 3 of the patients (75%) recovered completely, and 1 did not recover completely at the 4-month follow-up.

Conclusion: Foot drop is an important cause of walking disorder and greatly affects the quality of life. While it can be damaged due to trauma in the foreground, viral infections are also involved in the etiology. Although the prognosis varies depending on the etiology, the prognosis is generally good.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Peroneal nerve damage, drop foot

INTRODUCTION

Another cause of gait disorders is peroneal nerve damage. The peroneal nerve, which branches off from the sciatic nerve in the popliteal fossa, passes the lateral head of the gastrocnemius muscle on the outer surface of the popliteal fossa (Şimşek, 2021). The peroneal nerve provides plantar flexion of the foot. Since plantar flexion cannot be performed when damaged, foot drop occurs. Patients present with complaints of gait deterioration. Trauma, sharp injuries, bone fractures, viral infections may cause this condition (Baima & Krivichas, 2008). Treatment includes rest, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, physical therapy, and surgery if necessary (Garazzo, Ferraresi, & Buffatti, 2004).

CASE PRESENTATION

We wanted to present 4 cases with etiologies who presented with foot drop between January 2018 and January 2025.

Case 1: A 4-year-old male patient suffered trauma to his leg after falling 2 weeks ago. He was told that there might be a fissure in the tibial bone and was given a half splint for immobilization. The splint was removed after 1 week, but walking disorder was observed in the leg where the splint was removed. On examination, there was drop foot and 4/5 loss of strength. Patellar reflex was bilateral. Spinal imaging was normal. It was thought that there might be peroneal nerve damage due to the slipping of the splint. After non-steroidal anti-inflammatory treatment, his complaints completely regressed within 1 week.

Case 2: A 7-year-old female patient came to the pediatric emergency room with walking disorder. On examination, bilateral drop foot was detected. Spinal imaging was normal. Neurological examination was normal. There was a history of flu two weeks ago. The patient's walking gradually improved within 1 month. Peroneal nerve damage due to viral infection was considered.

Case 3: A 10-year-old male patient was hit in the peroneal nerve region while playing football with his father, and after the acute period passed, the patient's walking was impaired. On examination, drop foot was observed on that side, patellar reflexes were bilateral, and neurological examination was normal. Improvement was observed within 10 days with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory treatment.

Case 4: A 15-year-old male underwent surgery for a gunshot wound to the leg region. When mobilized, gait was impaired. On examination, drop foot was detected. Spinal imaging was normal. Peroneal nerve damage was detected on EMG. Physical therapy was recommended to the patient. After 4 months, there was partial improvement in walking, and he still could not perform plantar flexion fully. The patient did not come for follow-ups afterwards. Between January 2018 and January 2025, 4 pediatric patients presented with foot drop clinic and were diagnosed with peroneal nerve palsy. 3 of the patients (75%) were male and 1 was female (25%). The clinic of 3 of the patients (75%) was due to trauma and 1 (25%) was secondary to viral infections. All of the patients were male and peroneal nerve damage was observed on one side of the leg in the trauma area. In the only case that developed viral infection, the findings were observed bilaterally. 3 of the patients (75%) recovered completely, and 1 did not show complete recovery in the 4-month follow-ups.

DISCUSSION

The sciatic nerve is the largest nerve in the body, and the peroneal nerve branches off the sciatic nerve at the kneecap. The peroneal nerve is sensitive to trauma because it runs on the surface. It is the most common cause of foot drop. There are many different etiologies for peroneal nerve damage. While trauma is the most common of these, hematoma, vascular infarction, neuropathy, tumor formation, infection, and inflammation are also considered as causes (Şimşek, 2021; Altıntaş et al., 2016). In our cases, trauma was also evaluated as the most common cause with a rate of 75%. All cases with trauma were male. Treatment includes rest, non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs, and surgery if necessary (Garazzo, Ferraresi, & Buffatti, 2004). Prognosis varies depending on etiology, 3 patients (75%) recovered completely within 1 month, while 1 patient partially recovered after 4 months.

Drop foot is an important cause of walking disorder and greatly affects the quality of life. While it can be damaged due to trauma in the foreground, viral infections are also included in the etiology. Although the prognosis varies depending on the etiology, the prognosis is generally good.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Altıntaş, A., Gündüz, A., Kantarcı, F., & Çelik, G. G. (2016). Sciatic neuropathy developed after injection during curettage. *Agri*, 28(1), 46–48.
- Baima, J., & Krivickas, L. S. (2008). Evaluation and treatment of peroneal neuropathy. *Current Reviews in Musculoskeletal Medicine*, 1(2), 147–153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12178-008-9025-5>
- Garozzo, D., Ferraresi, S., & Buffatti, P. (2004). Surgical treatment of common peroneal nerve injuries: Indications and results: A series of 62 cases. *Journal of Neurosurgical Sciences*, 48(3), 105–112.
- Şimşek, F. (2021). Düşük ayak kliniği ile başvuran hastaların etiyolojik, elektrofizyolojik ve prognostik özellikleri. *İstanbul Medipol Tıp Dergisi*, 4(2), 120–123.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Sevgi Cirakli
Ordu University Education and Research Hospital, Ordu, Turkey
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7992-1376>
sevgigumusoglu@hotmail.com